

1 **Transcriptional properties of the homeobox transcription factor TGIF1.**

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6 Expression of a p53 mutant found in humans that is sufficient to result in cancer, R175H, resulted in
7 induction of a homeobox transcription factor, R175H. We used mouse embryonic stem cells engineered to
8 lack TGIF1 expression and mouse embryonic fibroblasts isolated from TGIF knockout mice (TGIF1^{-/-}) to
9 study gene expression regulation by TGIF1. TGIF1 existed at the head of a hierarchy of homeobox
10 factors, and controlled expression of the stem cell homeobox transcription factors NONO and a homeobox
11 factor functioning in mesoderm specification in human embryonic stem cells, TBX3. Study of whole gene
12 expression in primary tumors from humans with breast cancer revealed TGIF1 is a differentially expressed
13 gene in humans with HER2+ breast cancer, expressed at high levels in the primary tumor at clinical
14 presentation. TGIF1 controlled expression of a network of epigenetic molecules including Mbd4, KDM1A,
15 DNMT1 and Phf20, and regulated expression of the oncogene KRas. Depletion of TGIF1 resulted in the
16 loss of expression of PARP1, DNA-PKc (PRKDC) and Atr, indicating a DNA repair event associated with
17 TGIF1 induction or induction of homeoboxes in general. The data describe a gene expression program
18 regulated by TGIF1 and suggest homeobox transcription factor expression may be a necessary event in
19 transformation leading to human cancer.
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Results

We measured total transcription in embryonic fibroblasts from TGIF1 knock-out mice and murine embryonic stem cells with engineered deletion of TGIF1 (mES TGIF1 -/-)

Figure 1: TGIF1 controls the expression of homeobox transcription factors NONO and TBX3.

Figure 1a. Primary mouse embryonic fibroblasts (MEFs) from TGIF1 -/- mice.

GSE24225

ID	p-value	t	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	%DE
1415820_x_at	1.95E-02	4.25	-5.4363	6.10E-02	Nono	1705/	96.2
1437479_x_at	9.98E-02	2.27	-7.4391	2.44E-01	Tbx3	4521/45102	90.0

Figure 1b. TGIF1 -/- embryonic stem cells.

GSE55437

ID	p-value	t	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	%DE
1431239_at	6.06E-03	3.839074	-2.819437	0.43616082	Nono	4480/	80.3
1448029_at	5.00E-05	8.567455	2.382047	2.42739401	Tbx3	879/22690	96.1

Figure 2: TGIF1 controls expression of a network of epigenetic molecules.

Figure 2a. Primary mouse embryonic fibroblasts (MEFs) from TGIF1 -/- mice.

ID	p-value	t	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	%DE
1441079_at	2.45E-01	1.41	-8.4461	5.05E-02	Mbd4	9666/	78.6
1426761_at	2.06E-01	1.57	-8.2614	7.13E-02	Kdm1a	7605/	83.1
1458017_at	2.73E-02	3.78	-5.8596	1.53E-01	Phf20	2131/	95.3
1422946_a_at	1.20E-01	2.08	-7.6569	1.85E-01	Dnmt1	5067/45102	88.8

Figure 2b. TGIF1 -/- embryonic stem cells.

ID	p-value	t	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	%DE
1449490_at	6.39E-05	8.256454	2.118542	0.67749612	Mbd4	978/	95.7
1426761_at	3.66E-04	6.28609	0.222129	0.60528315	Kdm1a	1824/	92.0
1452258_at	7.86E-04	5.545642	-0.60928	0.37012963	Phf20	2397/	89.4
1435122_x_at	1.12E-03	5.22345	-0.994343	0.36422783	Dnmt1	2698/22690	88.1

Figure 3: TGIF1 regulation of zinc finger proteins.

Figure 3a. Primary mouse embryonic fibroblasts (MEFs) from TGIF1 -/- mice.

ID	p-value	t	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	%DE
1433953_at	9.26E-02	2.34	-7.3511	5.01E-01	Zfp277	4322/	90.4
1449126_at	1.78E-02	4.39	-5.3194	2.21E-01	Zfp90	1607/	96.4
1452340_at	1.13E-01	2.14	-7.5821	1.81E-01	Zfp518b	4844/45102	89.3

ID	p-value	t	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	%DE
1433953_at	3.66E-04	6.287473	0.223616	0.39816899	Zfp277	1823/	92.0
1449126_at	3.17E-02	2.658458	-4.565487	0.22014238	Zfp90	7193/	68.3
1452340_at	7.28E-04	5.617222	-0.5257	0.4272657	Zfp518b	2335/22690	89.7

Figure 4: TGIF1 regulates molecules with functions in thyroid hormone signaling.

Figure 4a. Primary mouse embryonic fibroblasts (MEFs) from TGIF1 ^{-/-} mice.

ID	p-value	t	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	%DE
1423899_at	1.06E-01	2.21	-7.5117	2.62E-01	Trip12	4672/	89.6
1429295_s_at	2.29E-02	4.02	-5.6418	7.44E-01	Trip13	1914/	95.8
1422973_a_at	1.31E-01	2	-7.7562	6.35E-02	Thrsp	5362/45102	88.1

Figure 4b. TGIF1 ^{-/-} embryonic stem cells.

ID	p-value	t	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	%DE
1423899_at	2.23E-06	13.533583	5.668874	1.0778429	Trip12	229/	99.0
1424737_at	2.81E-05	9.339982	3.000798	1.74098246	Thrsp	693/22690	69.3

Figure 5: A DNA damage signaling event associated with TGIF1 homeobox induction and repression. PARP1, DNA-PKc (PRKDC) and Atr

Figure 5a. Primary mouse embryonic fibroblasts (MEFs) from TGIF1 ^{-/-} mice.

ID	p-value	t	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	%DE
1422502_at	8.96E-02	2.38	-7.3116	3.28E-01	Parp1	4235/	90.6
1451576_at	2.17E-01	1.52	-8.3176	2.51E-01	Prkdc	7988/	82.3
1445091_at	1.35E-02	4.82	-4.9758	2.96E-01	Atr	1371/45102	97.0

Figure 5b. TGIF1 ^{-/-} embryonic stem cells.

ID	p-value	t	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	%DE
1422502_at	4.22E-05	8.791452	2.566561	0.8672054	Parp1	813/	96.4
1451576_at	2.98E-05	9.262045	2.940569	0.68957058	Prkdc	708/	96.9
1427197_at	3.33E-05	9.106418	2.818871	0.77091538	Atr	740/22690	96.7

Discussion

We demonstrated here hierarchical organization of homeobox factors, with control of expression of the stem cell homeobox transcription factors NONO and a homeobox factor functioning in mesoderm specification in human embryonic stem cells, TBX3 by the homeobox factor TGIF1. Interestingly, we found that TGIF1 controlled the expression of a network of molecules with epigenetic function including Mbd4 and Dnmt1.